

The Role of Acupuncture in Depression Management: Insights on evidence and treatment options.

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Abstract: Depression, a prevalent mental health disorder, significantly impacts individuals' quality of life. While conventional treatments like medication and psychotherapy are effective, some individuals may benefit from complementary therapies. Acupuncture, a core component of Traditional Chinese Medicine, has garnered attention as a potential adjunctive treatment for depression.

By stimulating specific acupuncture points, acupuncture can influence the body's energy levels, neurotransmitter systems, and neuroendocrine regulation. This can lead to relieving depressive symptoms, such as sadness, fatigue, and loss of interest. Several studies, including meta-analyses, have demonstrated the efficacy of acupuncture in reducing depressive symptoms, particularly when combined with conventional treatments. However, the specific mechanisms underlying acupuncture's effects on depression remain to be fully elucidated.

While acupuncture offers a promising approach to managing depression, further research is needed to establish standardized treatment protocols, optimize dosage and treatment duration, and assess long-term outcomes. Additionally, large-scale, well-designed randomized controlled trials are essential to strengthen the evidence base.

By addressing these limitations and pursuing further research, it will be possible to understand the full potential of acupuncture as a complementary tool in the treatment of depression.

Keywords: Depression; Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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1. Introduction

Ancient Chinese medical texts laid the foundation for many principles still utilized in modern Chinese medicine ¹. In the chapter on Pathogenic Wind of the *Ling Shu* ², it is written that the Yellow Emperor said: "In a way, all sick people know the causes of their illnesses, as the Master has already explained. But there are those who find no pathogenic influence and have no worries or fears in their minds, yet they still fall ill suddenly."

Most patients with depression are treated in primary care settings within Western medicine and do not require hospitalization. Primary care guidelines typically recommend that depression be managed primarily with antidepressants ³. A variety of psychological interventions, including cognitive-behavioural therapy, interpersonal therapy, psychotherapy, and counselling, are also recommended treatment options ³⁻⁵. However, conventional medications can have side effects, the effectiveness of psychological interventions can vary depending on factors such as therapist expertise, patient engagement, and the specific therapy used, and certain treatment-resistant types of depression may develop ⁶⁻⁹.

Several research studies have explored the treatment of depression using Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) ¹⁰⁻¹⁸. This study aims to actively contribute to clinical research by implementing TCM therapies in practice and to verify their efficacy and potential for enhancing the treatment of this disorder. While the study will provide some background information on depression from a Western perspective, the primary focus will be on TCM.

2. Depression

Modern society, with its fast-paced lifestyle and numerous challenges, can significantly impact mental health, leading to negative consequences for individuals, families, and society as a whole ¹⁹⁻²⁵.

The World Health Organization ^{26,27} states that over 50% of the population in middle- and high-income countries will experience at least one mental disorder during their lifetime. As mental illness affects people from all walks of life, it is a major public health concern with far-reaching implications.

Depression, a common mental health disorder, can manifest in various ways and significantly affect individuals globally. The National Institute of Mental Health ²⁸ defines depression as a serious mood disorder that can disrupt daily functioning, cognitive processes, and behaviour. Symptoms include persistent sadness, hopelessness, irritability, and a loss of interest in activities. Depression is a leading cause of disability worldwide, affecting approximately 300 million people and increasing by 18.4% from 2005 to 2015 ²⁹. Furthermore, it is a major risk factor for suicide, with approximately 800,000 deaths annually ²⁷.

In severe cases, symptoms may appear without any apparent connection to traumatic life events and can last for several months. In milder forms, symptoms are less intense, allowing individuals to maintain their daily activities, although feelings of fatigue, sadness, and disinterest are present and may persist for years. In some cases, depression does not manifest as sadness but through symptoms such as fatigue, nonspecific pain, chest tightness, insomnia, and digestive disturbances (nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea), which can lead to misdiagnosis and delay treatment ³⁰⁻³³.

Generally, depression results from a combination of genetic, biological, environmental, and psychological factors ³⁴⁻³⁶.

3. Depression and TCM

TCM, a system rooted in millennia of philosophical and observational wisdom, is based on principles such as the five elements, *Yin* and *Yang*, the circulation of *Qi* and Blood, and the importance of *Zang-Fu* organs ³⁷⁻⁴¹. These principles view the human body as a microcosm, reflecting the patterns of nature ³⁷.

TCM recognizes the influence of seasonal changes, daily cycles, and emotions on the body's energy balance. This holistic approach to health and disease emphasizes the importance of maintaining energy balance to prevent illness ⁴².

According to Silva ⁴³ and Ferreira *et al.* ³⁷, TCM views depression as an imbalance in the flow of *Qi* (vital energy) and Blood, often affecting organs like the liver and heart. This imbalance can manifest in physical and emotional symptoms, highlighting the intricate connection between mind and body.

In conventional Medicine, psychiatry is a complex field and mental illnesses frequently coexist with other mental and physical conditions ⁴⁴. Table 1, adapted from Soares Bernardo ⁴², provides a comparative analysis of TCM and conventional Medicine depression patterns, based on common symptoms.

3.1. Acupuncture for depression

From a scientific perspective, acupuncture engages multiple physiological mechanisms. When an acupuncture point is stimulated, it initiates a complex neural response, resulting in the release of various neurotransmitters and hormones ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷. These neurochemical changes can alleviate pain, reduce inflammation, and mitigate stress; thereby promoting overall well-being ⁴⁶. Acupuncture is believed to harmonize the body's physiological functions.

Several studies investigate the application of acupuncture in patients with depression.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of TCM and conventional Medicine depression patterns, adapted from Soares Bernardo ⁴².

TCM Pattern	Conventional Diagnosis	Common Symptoms
Qi Stagnation	Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder, Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder	Chest tightness, irritability, abdominal distension, irritability, temper outbursts
Heart Fire	Major Depressive Disorder, Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder	Insomnia, mental agitation, intense emotions, affective lability, anxiety
Qi and Blood Deficiency	Major Depressive Disorder, Persistent Depressive Disorder	Fatigue, weakness, lack of concentration
Dampness and Cold Accumulation	Major Depressive Disorder	Lethargy, mental fog, heaviness
Kidney Deficiency	Major Depressive Disorder, Persistent Depressive Disorder, Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder	Chronic fatigue, lack of motivation, difficulty concentrating, decreased interest
Interior Wind Upward Disturbance	Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder, Major Depressive Disorder, Persistent Depressive Disorder	Intrusive thoughts, irritability, mental agitation, low self-esteem, hopelessness
Wind-Cold Attack	N/A	Aversion to cold, lethargy, body aches
Blood Stagnation	Persistent Depressive Disorder, Major Depressive Disorder	Persistent pain, obsessive thoughts, emotional heaviness, low self-esteem, hopelessness

A meta-analysis by Chan *et al.* ⁴⁸ examined the effectiveness of combining acupuncture and antidepressant medication for the treatment of depression. The authors identified clinical studies comparing the combination therapy to antidepressant monotherapy. The results consistently demonstrated that the combination approach was superior in reducing depressive symptoms. This suggests that acupuncture can augment the therapeutic benefits of antidepressant medication. The synergistic effect may be attributed to the complementary mechanisms of action of these two modalities, which target various physiological systems involved in mood regulation.

Another meta-analysis conducted by Smith *et al.* ⁴⁹ investigated the efficacy of acupuncture as an intervention for depression. The findings suggest that acupuncture may have a positive impact on depressive symptoms. When combined with antidepressant medication, acupuncture was found to be more effective in reducing depression severity and minimizing medication-related side effects compared to medication alone. However, the combination therapy did not demonstrate significant advantages in terms of achieving remission from depression or improving emotional quality of life. In comparison to psychological therapy, acupuncture showed superior short-term outcomes and fewer adverse effects. However, the long-term benefits of acupuncture in terms of reducing depression severity were less pronounced compared to psychological therapy.

Furthermore, the meta-analysis by Armour *et al.* ⁵⁰ synthesized data from multiple clinical trials involving depressed patients who received acupuncture or a control intervention (e.g., placebo, no treatment). The findings consistently indicated that acupuncture was significantly more effective in reducing depressive symptoms compared to control conditions. This suggests that acupuncture may be a valuable therapeutic option for patients with depression. The observed benefits may be related to acupuncture's ability to harmonize the body's energy flow, alleviate stress and tension, and stimulate the release of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and dopamine, which are implicated in mood regulation.

The recent systematic review and network meta-analysis by Chen *et al.*⁵¹ aimed to assess the efficacy and safety of acupuncture for depression. Twenty-two randomized controlled trials, published in English, were included in the analysis. The results of the network meta-analysis demonstrated that electroacupuncture combined with antidepressant medication was the most effective treatment, followed by manual acupuncture combined with antidepressants and manual acupuncture alone. These findings suggest that acupuncture, either as a standalone treatment or as an adjunct to pharmacological therapy, can be a safe and beneficial option for managing depression.

Based on the available scientific evidence, acupuncture appears to be a promising therapeutic option for managing depression, particularly when used in conjunction with conventional treatments.

3.1.1. Treatment options

The specific acupuncture points and meridians used in clinical practice for the treatment of depression vary depending on the acupuncturist's approach and the individual patient's needs. However, some common points and meridians can be suggested:

- *Baihui* (GV20): Located at the crown of the head, this point is often used to treat depression and anxiety.

Figure 1. Baihui acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization 1.

- *Yintang* (EX-HN3): Situated between the eyebrows, this point is commonly used for anxiety and depression.
- Heart Meridian (HT): This meridian is frequently used to treat anxiety and depression, and includes points like *Shenmen* (HT7).

Figure 2. *Shenmen* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

- Liver Meridian (LR): This meridian is often used for depression and includes points such as *Taichong* (LR3) and *Xingjian* (LR2).

Figure 3. *Taichong* and *Xingjian* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

- Spleen Meridian (SP): This meridian is commonly used for anxiety and depression, and includes points like *Sanyinjiao* (SP6) and *Taibai* (SP3).

Figure 4. *Sanyinjiao* and *Taibai* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

It is important to note that the specific acupuncture points and meridians used will vary based on the individual patient's assessment and the acupuncturist's diagnosis. While the points mentioned above are commonly used, others may be considered for treating depression, such as:

- *Hegu* (LI4): Located between the thumb and index finger, this point is often used for anxiety and depression.

Figure 5. *Hegu* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

- *Zusanli* (ST36): Found below the knee, this point is commonly used to treat fatigue and depression.

Figure 6. *Zusanli* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

- *Fengchi* (GB20): Located at the base of the skull, this point is often used for headaches and depression.

Figure 7. *Fengchi* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

- *Shenting* (GV24): Located at the top of the head, this point is commonly used for anxiety and depression.

- *Yifeng* (TE17): Located behind the ear, this point is frequently used for anxiety and depression.

Figure 9. *Yifeng* acupuncture point location. Retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

4. Final Remarks

The integration of TCM with Western medicine offers a promising approach to managing depression. Acupuncture, a core component of TCM, demonstrates the potential to

alleviate depressive symptoms and enhance overall well-being. By targeting the body's energy flow and neurotransmitter systems, acupuncture may provide additional therapeutic benefits, particularly when combined with conventional treatments.

While the evidence supporting the efficacy of acupuncture for depression is growing, several limitations should be acknowledged.

Studies on acupuncture often exhibit methodological heterogeneity, including variations in treatment protocols, patient populations, and outcome measures. This can make it challenging to draw definitive conclusions. As well, most studies have focused on short-term outcomes. Long-term studies are needed to assess the sustained effects of acupuncture on depression.

Worthy of consideration, the effectiveness of acupuncture may be influenced by cultural and contextual factors, such as patient expectations, therapist experience, and the specific cultural context of the treatment setting.

To further elucidate the mechanisms of action and optimize the clinical application of acupuncture for depression, future research should consider several aspects.

Developing standardized protocols for acupuncture treatment of depression can improve the consistency and reproducibility of research findings.

Moreover, investigating the underlying mechanisms of acupuncture's effects on depression, such as neurotransmitter modulation, neuroendocrine regulation, and immune system function, can deepen our understanding of its therapeutic potential.

It is also important to keep exploring the synergistic effects of acupuncture with other therapeutic modalities, such as medication and psychotherapy, to optimize treatment outcomes.

By addressing these limitations and pursuing further research, the scientific evidence may confirm the potential of acupuncture as a valuable tool in the management of depression.

5. Conclusions

Acupuncture, a cornerstone of Traditional Chinese Medicine, shows promise as a complementary treatment for depression. By modulating the body's energy flow and neurotransmitter systems, acupuncture can alleviate depressive symptoms, reduce stress, and improve overall well-being. While further research is needed to fully understand its mechanisms of action and optimize its clinical application, acupuncture offers a holistic approach to mental health that may benefit many individuals.

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